

PREVALENCE AND PREDICTORS OF TEENAGE PREGNANCY IN NIGERIA: EVIDENCE FROM 2018 NIGERIA DEMOGRAPHIC HEALTH SURVEY

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Abstract: Background: Adolescence is a critical stage of human development, during which lifestyle choices have long-term consequences on future health and wellbeing. Teenage pregnancy remains a major public health issue in Nigeria, with implications for education, health outcomes, and socio-economic development. This study examined the prevalence and predictors of teenage pregnancy using the 2018 Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS) dataset.

Methods: Data were obtained from the nationally representative 2018 NDHS household recode dataset, which employs a two-stage sampling design across 36 states and the Federal Capital Territory. The analysis included women aged 15–49 years. Descriptive statistics summarized the data, while chi-square tests and binary logistic regression identified associations between teenage pregnancy and explanatory variables. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$ (two-sided), and analyses were conducted using SPSS version 20.

Results: A total of 21,911 women aged 15–49 years were analyzed. Most respondents were married or in a union (94.2%), and the majority were Muslims (61.4%). Teenage pregnancy was significantly associated with several factors. Independent predictors included residing in the North East (AOR=1.61; 95% CI: 1.31–1.98), belonging to the poorer wealth class (AOR=1.64; 95% CI: 1.42–1.90), having no formal education (AOR=3.03; 95% CI: 2.44–3.76), and having only primary education (AOR=3.96; 95% CI: 3.21–4.90). Early sexual debut also increased the risk of teenage pregnancy ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: Teenage pregnancy prevalence remains high in Nigeria. Key predictors include education level, partner's education, residence, region, ethnicity, wealth index, and early sexual initiation. Strengthening adolescent-friendly reproductive health services is essential to mitigate this burden.

1. INTRODUCTION

Background

Teenage pregnancy, defined as pregnancy occurring between the ages of 13 and 19 years, remains a major public health and social concern globally, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa (Kassa et al., 2018; Madlala et al., 2018; Worku et al., 2021). It is associated with disproportionately higher risks of morbidity and mortality for both mothers and infants compared with pregnancies among older women (Adedokun et al., 2016; Nwobodo & Panti, 2012; Ujah et al., 2005). Evidence consistently shows that adolescent mothers are more likely to experience adverse obstetric outcomes, including anaemia, hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, prolonged or obstructed labour, unsafe abortion, preterm delivery, increased operative deliveries due to pelvic immaturity, low birth weight, and neonatal mortality (Ebeigbe & Gharoro, 2007; Grønvik et al., 2018; Annan et al., 2021; Serunjogi et al., 2021).

Beyond health consequences, teenage pregnancy has profound social and economic implications. These include increased rates of school dropout, limited educational attainment, restricted employment opportunities, social stigma, and child abandonment, all of which perpetuate intergenerational cycles of poverty (Engelbert Bain et al., 2020; Sarnquist et al., 2017; Stoner et al., 2019). While the prevalence of teenage pregnancy has declined substantially in many high-income countries, reductions have

been slower in low- and middle-income settings (Kassa et al., 2018). Estimates indicate that approximately 18.8% of adolescents in Africa and 19.3% in sub-Saharan Africa experience pregnancy, compared with much lower proportions in Eastern Asia (0.7%), South-Eastern Asia (4.5%), and Latin America (6.4%) (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2017).

Nigeria continues to record one of the highest burdens of teenage pregnancy in sub-Saharan Africa (Kassa et al., 2018). Findings from the 2018 Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS) show that approximately 106 per 1,000 women experienced pregnancy during adolescence. Overall, 19% of girls aged 15–19 years had begun childbearing, with 14% having already given birth and an additional 4% pregnant with their first child at the time of the survey (National Population Commission [NPC] & ICF, 2019). Marked regional disparities persist, with substantially higher rates in northern Nigeria compared with southern regions. Previous NDHS data indicate that teenage pregnancy prevalence ranges from about 8% in the South-West and South-East to as high as 36% in the North-West (NPC & ICF, 2014).

In response to these disparities, Nigerian federal and state governments have implemented programmes promoting sexual abstinence, contraceptive use, and sexuality education among adolescents. However, the effectiveness of these interventions remains

limited. Cultural norms that encourage early marriage and childbearing, particularly within traditional African societies, continue to shape adolescent reproductive behaviour (Treffers, 2003; United Nations Population Fund, 2003). Early marriage, limited educational opportunities for girls, and entrenched gender norms further reinforce early childbearing (Ezra & Gurmu, 2002; Henry et al., 2012).

Existing literature has identified multiple risk factors for teenage pregnancy, including early sexual debut, cohabitation, inadequate or inconsistent contraceptive use, low educational attainment, poverty, sexual violence, family structure, and sociocultural approval of premarital pregnancy (Ajala, 2014; Avogo & Somefun, 2019; Bamiwuye, 2014; Chau-Kuang et al., 2013; Yakubu & Salisu, 2018). Despite this body of evidence, gaps remain in understanding how these factors interact at a national level using recent, nationally representative data. Given the persistence of teenage pregnancy in Nigeria despite ongoing interventions, there is a need for updated empirical evidence to inform targeted policies and programmes. This study therefore examines the prevalence and predictors of teenage pregnancy in Nigeria using data from the 2018 NDHS.

Problem Statement

Teenage pregnancy remains a critical challenge among adolescents in Africa, with far-reaching health, social, and developmental consequences (Madlala et al., 2018; Worku et al., 2021). Traditionally, reproductive health interventions

have focused predominantly on girls and young women, with limited engagement of male adolescents (Vargas et al., 2017). Although the emergence of HIV/AIDS shifted attention towards male involvement in sexual and reproductive health programmes, gaps persist in adolescents' understanding of the consequences of early sexual activity (Paton et al., 2020).

Communication about sexuality between parents and adolescents remains limited in many African contexts, particularly among young men, contributing to risky sexual behaviours, unintended pregnancies, and sexually transmitted infections (Dagnachew et al., 2020; Isaksen et al., 2020; Manu et al., 2015; Othman et al., 2020). Parental concerns that sexuality education may promote sexual experimentation further constrain open dialogue. In addition, increasing exposure to digital media, globalization, and evolving social norms underscores the urgency of reassessing the drivers of teenage pregnancy in contemporary Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. What is the prevalence of teenage pregnancy in Nigeria?
2. What is the effect of early sexual debut on teenage pregnancy among Nigerians?
3. What is the relationship between socio-economic status and teenage pregnancy in Nigeria?
4. What is the association between educational attainment and teenage pregnancy in Nigeria?

5. Are there regional differences in teenage pregnancy across Nigeria?

Study Aim and Objectives

Aim: To examine the prevalence of teenage pregnancy and its associated factors in Nigeria.

Specific Objectives

1. To estimate the prevalence of teenage pregnancy in Nigeria.
2. To assess the effect of early sexual debut on teenage pregnancy.
3. To examine the relationship between socio-economic status and teenage pregnancy.
4. To determine the association between educational level and teenage pregnancy.
5. To assess regional variations in teenage pregnancy across Nigeria.

Null Hypotheses

1. There is no association between early sexual debut and teenage pregnancy in Nigeria.
2. There is no association between socio-economic status and teenage pregnancy in Nigeria.
3. There is no association between educational attainment and teenage pregnancy in Nigeria.
4. There is no association between region of residence and teenage pregnancy in Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Overview of Teenage Pregnancy and Early Motherhood

Adolescent pregnancy and early motherhood are global phenomena with important implications for public health policy and social development (Mollborn, 2017; World Health Organization, 2020). It is estimated that

approximately 10 million pregnancies occur annually among girls aged 15–19 years, with the vast majority occurring in low- and middle-income countries. Adolescent birth rates are commonly reported for two age categories—10–14 years and 15–19 years—although reliable data for the younger age group remain limited due to underreporting and relatively low fertility rates (Maly et al., 2017). Consequently, most epidemiological evidence on adolescent pregnancy focuses on late adolescence (15–19 years) (Maly et al., 2017).

Globally, the average adolescent birth rate has been estimated at 44 births per 1,000 girls aged 15–19 years (United Nations Children’s Fund [UNICEF], 2021). While this figure reflects a gradual decline over the past decade, regional disparities remain pronounced. Between 2005 and 2015, the global adolescent birth rate decreased by approximately 11.6%, yet reductions have been uneven across regions (Ganchimeg et al., 2014). The highest adolescent birth rates have been reported in Central and West Africa, with an average of 115 live births per 1,000 girls aged 15–19 years, whereas Europe records the lowest rates, at approximately 13 live births per 1,000 adolescents (UNICEF, 2021). Comparisons across income settings further show that adolescent fertility rates are substantially lower in high-income countries, while rates in Central and West Africa remain more than twice the global average (UNICEF, 2021).

Nigeria records one of the highest adolescent birth rates globally, with an estimated 120 live

births per 1,000 girls aged 15–19 years (World Bank, 2019). Although this rate is lower than that reported in some neighbouring West and Central African countries, Nigeria's large population—estimated at over 205 million—means that even modest fertility rates translate into substantial absolute numbers. It is estimated that approximately 1.6 million births annually in Nigeria occur among adolescents aged 15–19 years (World Bank, 2019). Data from the 2018 Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS) indicate that 19% of girls aged 15–19 years had begun childbearing, with 14% having already given birth and an additional 4% pregnant with their first child at the time of the survey (National Population Commission [NPC] & ICF, 2019).

Correlates of Teenage Pregnancy and Early Motherhood in Nigeria

Several interrelated factors have been identified as contributors to teenage pregnancy and early motherhood in Nigeria. These include sexual violence and coercion, poverty and economic deprivation, and family structure and dynamics.

Sexual Violence and Coercion

Sexual violence and coercion are significant but often underreported determinants of teenage pregnancy. Sexual coercion alters power dynamics within relationships and limits adolescents' ability to negotiate safe sexual practices (Harris et al., 2009). National estimates suggest that approximately one in four girls in Nigeria experiences some form of sexual violence before the age of 18 (NPC, UNICEF Nigeria & CDC, 2016). Hospital-based

studies further demonstrate the vulnerability of adolescent girls. A review of sexual assault cases at a tertiary hospital in South-Western Nigeria reported that over 80% of victims were females younger than 19 years (Akinlusi et al., 2014), while a similar study in South-Eastern Nigeria found that nearly 70% of reported cases involved girls under 18 years, many of whom knew their assailants (Ohayi et al., 2015).

Systematic reviews also indicate that between 4% and 6% of female adolescents in Nigeria experience sexual assault, often perpetrated by individuals known to them (Folayan et al., 2014). Despite rape being criminalised in Nigeria, reporting rates remain low, with fewer than 5% of victims reporting incidents to authorities, largely due to stigma, fear of blame, and social repercussions (Folayan et al., 2014; Ibrahim et al., 2017; Olatunji, 2012). The combination of sexual violence, limited sexual and reproductive health knowledge, and a culture of silence surrounding abuse increases adolescents' vulnerability to unintended pregnancy. Evidence from high-income settings similarly demonstrates a strong association between childhood sexual abuse and teenage pregnancy (Roberts et al., 2004).

Gender norms further exacerbate these risks. Socialisation processes that encourage male sexual dominance and female passivity can pressure girls into unwanted sexual encounters, including exploitative relationships with authority figures such as teachers (Envuladu et al., 2017; Odimegwu & Somefun, 2017). Qualitative studies have highlighted adolescents'

limited ability to negotiate condom use within male-dominated relationships, further increasing the likelihood of unprotected sex and pregnancy (Envuladu et al., 2017).

Poverty

Economic deprivation is a central driver of teenage pregnancy in Nigeria. Adolescents from low socio-economic backgrounds are significantly more likely to experience early pregnancy compared with those from wealthier households (Amoran, 2012). NDHS data show striking disparities, with teenage pregnancy prevalence of approximately 33% among girls from the poorest households compared with about 3% among those from the wealthiest households (NPC & ICF, 2019).

Poverty increases adolescents' vulnerability to transactional and intergenerational sexual relationships, which are often rooted in economic necessity and gender inequality (Ankomah et al., 2011; Tade & Adekoya, 2012; Wamoyi et al., 2019). In such relationships, older male partners typically provide financial support or material goods in exchange for sex, limiting young women's autonomy and ability to negotiate safer sexual practices (Oyediran et al., 2011). Nigerian studies indicate that adolescents may engage in transactional sex to meet educational expenses, such as school fees and supplies (Achema et al., 2015).

Power imbalances inherent in these relationships heighten girls' susceptibility to sexual exploitation, unintended pregnancy, and sexually transmitted infections (Achema et al., 2015; Williams et al., 2012). Although

intergenerational transactional sex is widely regarded as exploitative, many adolescent girls do not perceive these relationships as abusive, viewing them instead as pragmatic responses to economic hardship (Wamoyi et al., 2010; Wamoyi et al., 2019). Evidence from South-Western Nigeria suggests that some adolescents actively seek financially supportive partners as a coping strategy, reflecting constrained choices rather than genuine empowerment (Kunnuji, 2014).

Family Setting

Family structure and dynamics also play a role in shaping adolescents' reproductive outcomes, although evidence in the Nigerian context remains limited. Available studies suggest that adolescents from single-parent households are more likely to experience teenage pregnancy compared with those from two-parent families (Odu & Christian, 2007). Similarly, higher rates of teenage pregnancy have been observed among girls from polygamous households compared with those from monogamous families (Envuladu et al., 2014).

These patterns may reflect reduced parental supervision, economic strain, and limited access to resources within certain family structures. Adolescents from large or economically constrained households may be more likely to engage in transactional sex to supplement household income or meet personal needs, thereby increasing their risk of early pregnancy (Wamoyi et al., 2018). Collectively, these findings highlight the importance of family context in understanding adolescents'

vulnerability to teenage pregnancy and early motherhood in Nigeria.

3. METHODOLOGY

Data Source and Study Design

This study utilised data from the 2018 Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS) household recode dataset. The NDHS is a nationally representative, cross-sectional survey designed to collect information on population health indicators among women, men, and children in Nigeria. The survey employed a two-stage stratified sampling design covering all 36 states and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) to ensure national and regional representativeness (National Population Commission [NPC] & ICF, 2019).

Figure 1: Summary of data extraction procedure

Figure 1 above shows the summary of data extraction procedure for the study.

Study Population

The study population comprised women aged 15–49 years who participated in the 2018 NDHS and had complete information on reproductive

history. In the first stage, enumeration areas were selected using probability proportional to size. In the second stage, households were systematically sampled within selected enumeration areas. The 2018 NDHS collected data on a wide range of health-related variables, including fertility, reproductive health, maternal healthcare utilisation, and socio-demographic characteristics. The present analysis followed established reporting guidelines for observational studies (DHS Program, 2021).

To account for the complex survey design and unequal probability of selection, sampling weights provided by NDHS were applied to all analyses to ensure representativeness at the national level (DHS Program, 2015). The data extraction procedure was shown in Figure 1.

history. Although teenage pregnancy refers to pregnancy occurring before the age of 20 years, analysing women aged 15–49 years enabled the assessment of lifetime history of adolescent

pregnancy within a nationally representative sample.

Outcome Variable

The primary outcome variable was teenage pregnancy, defined as having experienced a pregnancy or childbirth before the age of 20 years. This variable was derived from respondents' reported age at first birth or current pregnancy status.

The outcome was coded as a binary variable:

1 = Yes (experienced teenage pregnancy)

0 = No (did not experience teenage pregnancy)

Explanatory Variables

Based on existing literature and data availability in the NDHS, the following explanatory variables were included:

1. Socio-demographic factors: age, region of residence, place of residence (urban/rural), ethnicity, religion, and wealth index

2. Educational factors: respondent's highest level of education and partner's highest level of education

3. Sexual and reproductive factors: age at sexual debut (early sexual debut defined as initiation of sexual intercourse before age 16), antenatal care attendance, and timing of first antenatal visit

These variables were selected due to their established associations with adolescent pregnancy in prior studies.

Data Analysis

Data analysis was conducted using SPSS version 20. The analysis proceeded in three stages:

1. Univariate analysis: Frequencies and percentages were used to describe the distribution of all study variables. Variables

with more than 20% missing values were excluded from subsequent analyses, in line with established recommendations for handling missing data (Enders, 2003).

2. Bivariate analysis: The Chi-square test was used to assess associations between teenage pregnancy and each explanatory variable. Variables that showed statistically significant associations at this stage were considered for multivariable analysis.

3. Multivariable analysis: Binary logistic regression was employed to identify independent predictors of teenage pregnancy while adjusting for potential confounders. Results were reported as adjusted odds ratios (AORs) with corresponding 95% confidence intervals (CIs).

All statistical tests were two-sided, and statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for the 2018 NDHS was obtained by the Inner-City Fund (ICF) International Institutional Review Board and relevant national ethics committees. Permission to access and use the NDHS dataset was granted through the MEASURE DHS programme. The data used in this study were fully anonymised and publicly available, and no direct identifiers were accessible to the researchers. Therefore, no additional ethical approval was required for the present secondary data analysis. The dataset can be accessed at: <https://dhsprogram.com/data/available-datasets.cfm>

4. RESULTS

Socio-demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 1 presents the socio-demographic characteristics of the study participants. After applying sampling weights, a total of 21,911 women aged 15–49 years were included in the analysis. The majority of respondents were currently married or in a union (94.2%), while 2.3% had never been in a union and 3.5% were formerly married.

Geographically, respondents were predominantly from the North-West (34.9%) and North-East (17.6%), with smaller proportions from the South-West (14.7%), North-Central (13.8%), South-East (9.8%), and South-South (9.2%). With respect to socio-economic status, approximately one-fifth of

respondents belonged to each wealth quintile, although the poorest and poorer groups together accounted for over 40% of the sample.

Most respondents identified as Muslims (61.4%), while 38.1% were Christians. Hausa ethnicity constituted the largest ethnic group (36.0%), followed by Igbo (12.6%), Yoruba (12.6%), Fulani (8.0%), and other ethnic groups (30.8%). A greater proportion of respondents resided in rural areas (60.2%) compared with urban areas (39.8%).

Educational attainment was generally low: 44.4% of respondents had no formal education, and only 8.8% had attained higher education. Similarly, 36.1% of partners had no formal education, while 15.4% had completed higher education.

Table 1: Respondent’s demographic characteristics

Sociodemographic variables	Frequency	Percentage
Marital Status		
Never in union	514	2.3
Currently in union	20637	94.2
Formerly in union	760	3.5
Region		
North Central	3031	13.8
North East	3862	17.6
North West	7644	34.9
South East	2138	9.8
South South	2019	9.2
South West	3218	14.7
Wealth Index		
Poorest	4436	20.2
Poorer	4618	21.1

Middle	4608	21.0
Richer	4448	20.3
Richest	3802	17.4
Religion		
Christian	8344	38.1
Islam	13450	61.4
Traditionalist	73	0.3
Others	44	0.2
Ethnicity		
Igbo	2763	12.6
Hausa	7885	36.0
Yoruba	2760	12.6
Fulani	1741	8.0
Others	6748	30.8
Residence		
Urban	8712	39.8
Rural	13199	60.2
Educational Level		
No education	9738	44.4
Primary	3293	15.0
Secondary	6962	31.8
Higher	1919	8.8
Husband Educational level		
No education	7339	36.1
Primary	2834	14.0
Secondary	6998	34.5
Higher	3136	15.4

Table 1

shows the socio-demographic characteristics of the study participants.

Early Sexual Initiation and Antenatal Care Utilisation

As shown in Table 2, 65.6% of respondents reported early sexual debut, defined as initiation of sexual intercourse before the age of 16 years. Regarding antenatal care (ANC)

utilisation at first pregnancy, 75.2% attended at least one ANC visit, while 24.8% reported no ANC attendance. Among those who utilised ANC services, 57.8% attended four or more visits, whereas 17.4% attended fewer than four visits. The majority of women-initiated ANC

during the second trimester (62.9%), followed by the first trimester (24.2%) and the third trimester (12.8%). Government health facilities

were the most commonly utilised for ANC services (78.8%), compared with private facilities (18.3%) and other sources (0.4%).

Table 2: Respondent’s early sexual initiation status, antenatal care utilization

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Early Sex		
No	7535	34.4
Yes	14359	65.6
ANC Use		
No	5336	24.8
Yes	16217	75.2
ANC Quality		
No Visit	5336	24.8
<4 visits	3761	17.4
4 visits+	12456	57.8
Timing of ANC		
1st Trimester	4008	24.2
2nd Trimester	10411	62.9
3rd Trimester	2123	12.8
ANC at Government facility		
Yes	13069	78.8
No	3506	21.2
ANC at Private facility		
Yes	3038	18.3
No	13537	81.7
ANC at Other facility		
Yes	63	0.4
No	16512	99.6

Table 2, shows that 65.6% of respondents reported early sexual debut.

Prevalence of Teenage Pregnancy and Antenatal Care Patterns

Overall, 56.8% of women experienced their first pregnancy before the age of 20 years, indicating a high prevalence of teenage pregnancy in the

study population (Figure 2). Teenage pregnancy was associated with poorer antenatal care utilisation. A substantially higher proportion of women who experienced teenage pregnancy did not attend ANC at first pregnancy compared

with those whose first pregnancy occurred at older ages (73.1% vs 26.9%) (Figure 3). In addition, only 46.9% of women with a history of teenage pregnancy attended at least four ANC visits, compared with 53.1% among women whose first pregnancy occurred after adolescence. Delayed initiation of ANC was also

more common among women who experienced teenage pregnancy. Approximately 65.7% initiated ANC during the third trimester, compared with 34.3% among women whose first pregnancy occurred after age 20 years (Figure 4).

Figure 2: Prevalence of teenage pregnancy

Figure 3: Quality of ANC attended by types of pregnancy

Bivariate Analysis of Factors Associated with Teenage Pregnancy

All statistical analyses were conducted using two-sided tests, and results were considered statistically significant at a p-value of less than 0.05. Results of the bivariate analysis are presented in Tables 3a and 3b. The prevalence of teenage pregnancy differed significantly across socio-demographic and contextual factors ($p < 0.001$). Teenage pregnancy was more common among women who were currently in a union (57.2%) compared with those who had never been married (47.5%).

Marked regional differences were observed, with the highest prevalence recorded in the North-West (76.3%), followed by the North-East (71.8%) and North-Central (52.5%). In contrast, lower prevalence was observed in the South-East (27.5%), South-West (28.4%), and South-South (36.9%).

Teenage pregnancy showed a strong inverse relationship with wealth status. Women from the poorest households had the highest prevalence (72.3%), while those from the richer wealth quintile had substantially lower prevalence (49.0%). Similarly, teenage pregnancy was more common among women residing in rural areas (67.4%) compared with urban residents (40.8%).

Educational attainment was strongly associated with teenage pregnancy. Women with no formal education (76.4%) and those with only primary education (63.6%) had markedly higher prevalence compared with those who attained secondary (38.8%) or higher education (11.0%). Comparable patterns were observed with partners' educational levels. Early sexual debut was also significantly associated with teenage pregnancy, with 77.6% prevalence among those who initiated sex early compared with 17.0% among those who did not.

Table 3a: Bivariate analysis of factors associated with teenage pregnancy

Variables	Teenage Pregnancy		X ²	p-value
	Yes	No		
Marital Status				
Never in union	244 (47.5)	270 (52.5)		
Currently in union	11804 (57.2)	8833 (42.8)	26.01	<0.001
Formerly in union	397 (52.2)	363 (47.8%)		
Region				
North Central	1590 (52.5)	1441 (47.5)		
North East	2773 (71.8)	1089 (28.2)		
North West	5835 (76.3)	1809 (23.7)	3695.85	<0.001
South East	588 (27.5)	1550 (72.5)		
South South	745 (36.9)	1273 (63.1)		
South West	914 (28.4)	2303 (71.6)		
Wealth Index				
Poorest	3208 (72.3)	1227 (27.7)		
Poorer	3077 (66.6)	1541 (33.4)	1841.13	<0.001
Middle	2823 (61.3)	1784 (38.7)		
Richer	2178 (49.0)	2270 (51.0)		
Religion				
Christianity	2907 (34.8)	5437 (65.2)		
Islam	9467 (70.4)	3984 (29.6)	2654.81	<0.001
Traditionalist	49 (67.1)	24 (32.9)		
Others	23 (51.1)	22 (48.9)		
Ethnicity				
Igbo	707 (25.6)	2055 (74.4)		
Hausa	6052 (76.8)	1832 (23.2)		
Yoruba	765 (27.7)	1995 (72.3)	3775.29	<0.001
Fulani	1396 (80.2)	345 (19.8)		
Others	3519 (52.2)	3228 (47.8)		

Table 3b: Bivariate analysis of factors associated with teenage pregnancy

Variables	Teenage Pregnancy		X ²	p-value
	Yes	No		
Residence				
Urban	3553 (40.8)	5159 (59.2)		
Rural	8893 (67.4)	4306 (32.6)	1512.59	<0.001
Educational level				
No education	7438 (76.4)	2300 (23.6)		
Primary	2094 (63.6)	1199 (36.4)	4140.16	<0.001
Secondary	2701 (38.8)	4261 (61.2)		
Higher	212 (11.0)	1707 (89.0)		
Husband educational level				
No education	5640 (76.8)	1699 (23.2)		
Primary	1735 (61.2)	1099 (38.8)		
Secondary	3169 (45.3)	3830 (54.7)	2384.46	<0.001
Higher	1007 (32.1)	2130 (67.9)		
Early sex debut				
No	1280 (17.0)	6256 (83.0)		
Yes	11149 (77.6)	3210 (22.4)	7409.79	<0.001

In Table 3a and 3b, and figures 2-5, the prevalence of teenage pregnancy differed significantly across socio-demographic and contextual factors ($p < 0.001$); demonstrating statistical significance, at P value < 0.05

Multivariable Logistic Regression Analysis

Table 4 presents the results of the binary logistic regression analysis. After adjusting for potential confounders, several factors remained independently associated with teenage pregnancy.

Women residing in the North-East (AOR=1.61; 95% CI: 1.31–1.98) and North-West (AOR=1.50; 95% CI: 1.21–1.85) had significantly higher odds of experiencing teenage pregnancy compared

with those in the South-West. Socio-economic disadvantage was also a strong predictor, with women from the poorest, poorer, and middle wealth quintiles having significantly higher odds of teenage pregnancy compared with those in the richer quintile.

Educational attainment showed a strong protective effect. Women with no formal education (AOR=3.03; 95% CI: 2.44–3.76) and those with primary education (AOR=3.96; 95% CI: 3.21–4.90) were substantially more likely to experience teenage pregnancy compared with women who had attained higher education.

Early sexual debut remained a significant predictor, with women who did not initiate sex early showing markedly lower odds of teenage

pregnancy compared with those who did associated with reduced odds of teenage pregnancy relative to rural residence.

Table 4: Binary Logistic analysis of factors associated with teenage pregnancy

Variable	AOR	95% CI (AOR)		p value
		Lower	Upper	
Region				
North Central	1.28	1.06	1.55	0.010
North East	1.61	1.31	1.98	<0.001
North West	1.50	1.21	1.85	<0.001
South East	0.99	0.75	1.30	0.919
South South	0.88	0.71	1.1	0.219
South West (Ref)	1.00			
Wealth Index				
Poorest	1.64	1.42	1.90	<0.001
Poorer	1.59	1.39	1.82	<0.001
Middle	1.63	1.43	1.85	<0.001
Richer (Ref)	1.00			
Religion				
Christianity	0.98	0.47	2.04	0.948
Islam	1.51	0.71	3.18	0.283
Traditionalist	2.00	0.77	5.20	
Others (Ref)	1.00			
Ethnicity				
Igbo	0.72	0.57	0.90	0.004
Hausa	1.44	1.25	1.66	<0.001
Yoruba	0.69	0.56	0.83	<0.001
Fulani	1.51	1.27	1.79	<0.001
Others (Ref)	1.00			
Residence				
Urban	0.82	0.75	0.90	<0.001
Rural (Ref)	1.00			
Educational level				
No education	3.03	2.44	3.76	<0.001
Primary	3.96	3.21	4.90	<0.001
Secondary	2.86	2.36	3.45	<0.001

Higher (Ref)	1.00			
Partner’s educational level				
No education	0.97	0.83	1.13	0.687
Primary	1.16	0.99	1.36	0.069
Secondary	1.10	0.96	1.24	0.166
Higher (Ref)	1.00			
Early sex debut				
No	0.10	0.09	0.10	<0.001
Yes (Ref)	1.00			

In Table 4, after adjustment, teenage pregnancy in Nigeria was independently associated with residence in the North-East and North-West, lower socio-economic status, low educational attainment, early sexual debut, and rural residence, while higher education, delayed sexual initiation, and urban residence were protective.

5. DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATION

Discussion

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of the prevalence and predictors of teenage pregnancy in Nigeria using nationally representative data from the 2018 Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey. The findings demonstrate that teenage pregnancy remains highly prevalent in Nigeria, underscoring its continued public health and developmental significance. This pattern is consistent with evidence from other sub-Saharan African countries, including Uganda and Ghana, where adolescent pregnancy rates remain among the highest globally (Amongin et al., 2020; United

Nations Fund for Population Activities, 2013; Ahinkorah et al., 2021).

The high prevalence observed in this study aligns with global analyses showing that sub-Saharan Africa bears a disproportionate burden of adolescent pregnancy compared with other world regions (Huda et al., 2021). Persistent socio-economic inequalities, cultural norms supporting early marriage and childbearing, and limited access to comprehensive sexual and reproductive health services continue to shape adolescent reproductive outcomes in the region. Geographical variation emerged as a significant predictor of teenage pregnancy. Adolescents residing in the North-East and North-West regions had substantially higher odds of experiencing teenage pregnancy compared with those in the South-West. This finding mirrors earlier NDHS reports and other Nigerian studies that document higher fertility rates in northern regions, likely driven by early marriage, lower female educational attainment, poverty, and sociocultural norms favouring early childbearing (NPC & ICF, 2019; Ahinkorah et al., 2021). These regional disparities highlight the

need for context-specific interventions rather than uniform national strategies.

Socio-economic status was strongly associated with teenage pregnancy, with girls from poorer households experiencing significantly higher odds compared with those from wealthier households. This finding is consistent with prior studies across Nigeria and sub-Saharan Africa (Amaran, 2012; Yakubu & Salisu, 2018). Economic deprivation may increase vulnerability to transactional and intergenerational sexual relationships, limit educational opportunities, and restrict access to contraceptive services, thereby elevating the risk of early pregnancy.

Educational attainment emerged as one of the most robust protective factors against teenage pregnancy.

Adolescents with secondary or higher education were significantly less likely to experience early pregnancy compared with those with no formal or only primary education. This association has been widely reported in previous studies and may reflect increased reproductive health knowledge, delayed sexual initiation and marriage, and improved empowerment among educated girls (Wado et al., 2019; Poudel et al., 2018). Education also enhances adolescents' capacity to negotiate safer sexual practices and make informed reproductive choices.

Early sexual debut was a strong predictor of teenage pregnancy in this study. Adolescents who initiated sexual activity at younger ages were significantly more likely to experience pregnancy during adolescence. This finding

corroborates evidence from Nigeria and other sub-Saharan African settings, suggesting that delayed sexual debut reduces exposure to pregnancy risk and is often accompanied by greater awareness and use of contraceptive methods (Durowade et al., 2017; Yakubu & Salisu, 2018; Habito et al., 2019).

The study further revealed that teenage pregnancy was associated with suboptimal antenatal care utilisation. Adolescents were more likely to delay initiation of antenatal care, attend fewer visits, or not access antenatal services at all. This pattern has been reported in previous studies and may be attributable to stigma, limited autonomy, lack of knowledge, financial constraints, and restricted access to youth-friendly health services (Serunjogi et al., 2021). Poor antenatal care utilisation among adolescent mothers increases the risk of adverse maternal and neonatal outcomes, reinforcing the public health importance of preventing teenage pregnancy and improving care for those who become pregnant.

Conclusion

Teenage pregnancy remains highly prevalent in Nigeria and is strongly influenced by socio-economic, educational, regional, and behavioural factors. Key predictors identified in this study include region of residence, household wealth status, educational attainment of respondents, rural residence, and early sexual initiation. Teenage pregnancy was also associated with poorer antenatal care utilisation, characterised by delayed initiation and fewer visits. These findings underscore the

persistent inequalities that place Nigerian adolescents—particularly those in disadvantaged and rural settings—at heightened risk of early pregnancy and its adverse consequences.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Strengthen adolescent-friendly sexual and reproductive health services:

The government and health stakeholders should expand access to confidential, youth-friendly reproductive health services, particularly in rural and high-burden northern regions.

2. Promote and sustain girls' education: Policies that support girls' retention in secondary and higher education should be prioritised, as education remains one of the most effective protective factors against teenage pregnancy.

3. Address socio-economic vulnerabilities: Anti-poverty and social protection programmes should prioritise adolescent girls and young

REFERENCES

Achema, G., Emmanuel, A., & Moses, A. O. (2015). Factors responsible for teenage pregnancy and its implication on adolescent health and education: Perception of secondary school students in Nigeria. *International Journal of Medicine and Health Research*, 1(2), 48–51.

Adedokun, O., Adeyemi, O., & Dauda, C. (2016). Child marriage and maternal health risks among young mothers in Gombi, Adamawa State, Nigeria: Implications for

women, particularly those from low-income households, to reduce reliance on transactional sexual relationships.

4. Delay sexual debut through comprehensive sexuality education: Age-appropriate, culturally sensitive sexuality education should be strengthened in schools and communities, with active involvement of parents, teachers, and religious leaders.

5. Enhance male adolescent engagement: Sexual and reproductive health interventions should actively include boys and young men to promote shared responsibility, reduce coercive sexual practices, and improve reproductive health outcomes.

Further research:

Future studies should explore adolescents' perceptions of contraception, the role of stigma in healthcare utilisation, and longitudinal pathways linking education, poverty, and teenage pregnancy.

mortality, entitlements and freedoms. *African Health Sciences*, 16(4), 986–999.

Ahinkorah, B. O., Kang, M., Perry, L., Brooks, F., & Hayen, A. (2021). Prevalence of first adolescent pregnancy and its associated factors in sub-Saharan Africa: A multi-country analysis. *PLOS ONE*, 16(2), e0246308.

Ajala, A. O. (2014). Factors associated with teenage pregnancy and fertility in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 5(2), 52–61.

Akinlusi, F. M., Rabiun, K. A., Olawepo, T. A., Adewunmi, A. A., Ottun, T. A., & Akinola, O. I. (2014). Sexual assault in Lagos, Nigeria: A five-year retrospective review. *BMC Women's Health*, 14(1), 115.

Amongin, D., Nakimuli, A., Hanson, C., Nakafeero, M., Kaharuza, F., Atuyambe, L., & Benova, L. (2020). Time trends in and factors associated with repeat adolescent birth in Uganda: Analysis of six demographic and health surveys. *PLOS ONE*, 15(4), e0231557.

Amoran, O. E. (2012). A comparative analysis of predictors of teenage pregnancy and its prevention in a rural town in Western Nigeria. *International Journal for Equity in Health*, 11, 37.

Ankomah, A., Mamman-Daura, F., Omoregie, G., & Anyanti, J. (2011). Reasons for delaying or engaging in early sexual initiation among adolescents in Nigeria. *Adolescent Health, Medicine and Therapeutics*, 2, 75–84.

Annan, R. A., Gyimah, L. A., Apprey, C., Asamoah-Boakye, O., Aduku, L. N. E., Azanu, W., Luterodt, H. E., & Edusei, A. K. (2021). Predictors of adverse birth outcomes among pregnant adolescents in Ashanti Region, Ghana. *Journal of Nutritional Science*, 10, e33.

Avogo, W. A., & Somefun, O. D. (2019). Early marriage, cohabitation, and childbearing

in West Africa. *Journal of Environmental and Public Health*, 2019, 9731754.

Baatsen, P., Josaphat, J., Issa, R., Buwalda, A., & Juanola, L. (2018). Situation of teenage pregnancy and child marriage among in-school and out-of-school youth in Nampula and Rapale, Mozambique. Universidade Lúrio. <https://www.kit.nl/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/YID-Performance-study-MOZ-Nampula-Rapale.pdf>

Bamiwuye, S. O. (2014). Gender differentials in self-perception of risk and other barriers to HIV risk reduction practices among youths in Nigeria. *Journal of Demography and Social Statistics*, 1–13.

Chau-Kuang, C., Ward, C., Williams, K., & Abdullah, A. (2013). Investigating risk factors affecting teenage pregnancy rates in the United States. *European International Journal of Science and Technology*, 2(2), 41–51.

Dagnachew Adam, N., Demissie, G. D., & Gelagay, A. A. (2020). Parent–adolescent communication on sexual and reproductive health issues and associated factors among secondary school students in Northwest Ethiopia. *Journal of Environmental and Public Health*, 2020, 6898105.

Demographic and Health Surveys Program. (2015). Demonstration of how to weight DHS data. <https://dhsprogram.com>

Demographic and Health Surveys Program. (2021). Available datasets. <https://dhsprogram.com/data/available-datasets.cfm>

Durowade, K. A., Babatunde, O. A., Omokanye, L. O., Elegbede, O. E., Ayodele, L. M., Adewoye, K. R., & Olaniyan, T. O. (2017). Early sexual debut: Prevalence and risk factors among secondary school students in South-West Nigeria. *African Health Sciences*, 17(3), 614–622.

Ebeigbe, P. N., & Gharoro, E. P. (2007). Obstetric complications, intervention rates and maternofetal outcome in teenage nullipara in Benin City, Nigeria. *Tropical Doctor*, 37(2), 79–83.

Enders, C. K. (2003). Using the expectation maximization algorithm to estimate coefficient alpha for scales with item-level missing data. *Psychological Methods*, 8(3), 322–337.

Engelbert Bain, L., Amoakoh-Coleman, M., Tiendrebeogo, K. S. T., Zweekhorst, M. B., de Cock Buning, T., & Becquet, R. (2020). Attitudes towards abortion and decision-making capacity of pregnant adolescents in Ghana. *European Journal of Contraception & Reproductive Health Care*, 25(2), 151–158.

Envuladu, E. A., Agbo, H. A., Ohize, V. A., & Zoakah, A. I. (2014). Determinants and outcome of teenage pregnancy in a rural community in Nigeria. *Sub-Saharan African Journal of Medicine*, 1(1), 48–52.

Envuladu, E. A., Anke, V. D. K., Zwanikken, P., & Zoakah, A. I. (2017). Sexual and reproductive health challenges of adolescent males and females in Plateau State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Psychology and Behavioral Sciences*, 7(2), 55–60.

Ezra, M., & Gurmu, E. (2002). Correlates of marriage and family patterns in Southern Ethiopia. *Ethiopian Journal of Development Research*, 24(1), 58–59.

Folayan, M. O., Odetoyinbo, M., Harrison, A., & Brown, B. (2014). Rape in Nigeria: A silent epidemic among adolescents with implications for HIV infection. *Global Health Action*, 7(1), 25583.

Ganchimeg, T., Ota, E., Morisaki, N., Laopaiboon, M., Lumbiganon, P., Zhang, J., Temmerman, M., & Vogel, J. P. (2014). Pregnancy and childbirth outcomes among adolescent mothers: A WHO multicountry study. *BJOG: An International Journal of Obstetrics & Gynaecology*, 121(Suppl 1), 40–48.

Grønvik, T., & Fossgard Sandøy, I. (2018). Complications associated with adolescent childbearing in sub-Saharan Africa: A

systematic review and meta-analysis.
PLOS ONE, 13(9), e0204327.

Habito, C. M., Vaughan, C., & Morgan, A. (2019). Adolescent sexual initiation and pregnancy: Further analysis of DHS data. *BMC Public Health*, 19, 1514. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-019-7846-8>

Huda, M. M., O’Flaherty, M., Finlay, J. E., & Al Mamun, A. (2021). Time trends and sociodemographic inequalities in adolescent motherhood. *The Lancet Child & Adolescent Health*, 5(1), 26–36.

National Population Commission (NPC) [Nigeria] & ICF. (2014). *Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey 2013*. NPC and ICF.

National Population Commission (NPC) [Nigeria] & ICF. (2019). *Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey 2018*. NPC and ICF.

United Nations Children’s Fund. (2021). Early childbearing. <https://data.unicef.org/topic/child-health/adolescent-health/>

World Health Organization. (2020). Adolescent pregnancy. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/adolescent-pregnancy>

World Bank. (2019). Fertility rate, adolescent (births per 1,000 women ages 15–19). <https://data.worldbank.org>

Yakubu, I., & Salisu, W. J. (2018). Determinants of adolescent pregnancy in sub-Saharan Africa: A systematic review. *Reproductive Health*, 15(1), 15.

Zembe, Y. Z., Townsend, L., Thorson, A., & Ekström, A. M. (2013). “Money talks, bullshit walks”: Transactional sex among young women. *Globalization and Health*, 9(1), 10.

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Appendix I: Map of Nigeria

